

IS LGBT INCLUSION STEERING THE BOTTOM LINE? - A CORROBORATIVE BUSINESS CASE FOR LGBT INCLUSION IN THE WORKPLACE THROUGH HUMAN CAPITAL APPROACH

Amancherla Sowmya

Research Scholar, Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore, India

Email: amancherla.sowmya@res.christuniversity.in

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ABSTRACT

According to Brundtland's report, sustainable development is best understood as "to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs." (Sharma, 2009). However, sustainability does not restrict itself to restoring natural resources; it also means the inclusion of marginalized sections of the society, working and growing in tandem with them. This research deep dive into the relationship between LGBT inclusion and economic development, emphasizing the role of human capital approach in amplifying its direction and magnitude. This article, through various studies, asserts a compelling business case for LGBT inclusion in organisations. The study points out the economic impact of including gender and sexual minorities in society, and its importance of working and growing in tandem. Economists lament the ill effects of discrimination against these marginalised sections and highlight the unutilised human capital, which is 135 million Indian population and an untapped LGBT+ economy of US \$200 billion. This would have a domino effect on future generations and escalate the inequity even further, influencing the economy and society. Hence, it is imperative to accentuate LGBT inclusion as a compelling business case in the workplace.

Keywords : *LGBT inclusion, economic development, human capital, productivity, sexual orientation, gender identity*

INTRODUCTION

Diversity & Inclusion in India, precisely concerning the LGBT+ community, has been garnering increasing importance over the last two decades, specifically after the NALSA judgment of 2014 regarding the transgender person protection act and repealing of section 377 of IPC in 2018 pertaining to decriminalizing of homosexuality. However, the odyssey of LGBT in India goes farther than court cases and legal battles to representing personal stories, community efforts, media, eradicating HIV, promoting literacy, and striving for employability. Amongst these, financial security and career mentorship have always been pivotal aspirations. Organisations steadily recognize the importance of a diverse workforce because it is a moral responsibility to adhere to and because it poses a strong business case. The cognizance of this core principle that organizational performance and LGBT inclusion are directly correlated is the first step towards inclusivity in the workplace. Organizations that embrace an inclusive work culture position

themselves as aspirational places to work for in the global market, nurturing happy employees with higher retention rates. An inclusive workplace earns them lots of money, attracts and retains talented employees, enhances their innovation, strengthens their public relations, and helps them keep up with changing mindsets of the millennials. It is a complete win-win scenario (Shahani, 2020). For the last two decades, the legal system in India has been rapidly evolving and foraying into a more progressive space; the explicit testimonies are of the verdicts on transgender rights and decriminalising homosexuality. These judgments by the Supreme Court also warrant any ill-treatment of the gender and sexual minorities, thereby giving further impetus for inclusion

DISMANTLING THE ACRONYM

The term LGBT represents Lesbian, Gay, Bi-sexual, and Transgender. Lesbians are women who are physically, emotionally and sexually attracted to members of the same sex. Gay refers to men who are attracted physically, emotionally, or sexually attracted to members of the same sex. In comparison, bi-sexual people are physically, emotionally, and sexually attracted to both men and women. Transgender people are those individuals who do not comply with the gender norms or identity with that assigned at birth. It should also be noted that gender identity and sexual orientation are two different terms. Sexual orientation is the sexual inclination of an individual towards another individual, while gender identity is an internal sense and perception of one's gender. Gender expression is an external way of exhibiting one's gender identity through dress, hairstyle, and behavior (Rozatkar & Gupta, 2018).

THEORETICAL BASE

In the last few years, many economists and policymakers have supported that including LGBT individuals promulgates shared prosperity and economic development. In essence, denying the participation of LGBT people in society leads to an overt violation of their human rights. It could also subject them to discrimination and violence. This unfair treatment also casts its shadow on their right to health and education. These violations and exclusions are likely to be detrimental to a nation's economy and engender economic inefficiencies, including lost labor time, diminished productivity, underinvestment in human capital, and suboptimal allocation of human resources (Badgett et al., 2019). The insignificant contribution of human capital may stifle progress at a comprehensive macroeconomic level. Thus, the citizens' health attributes, skills, knowledge, and abilities determine the nation's productivity and leverage their overall economic behavior, substantiating the human capital theory argument for a clear interrelation between the inclusion of LGBT and economic progression (G Becker et al., 1990; Mincer, 1958).

Drawing on the above principle, embracing LGBT people into the workforce facilitates their quality education, robust vocational training, and wholesome health, catalysing a country's human capital and influencing productivity. Conversely, the exclusion of LGBT individuals in academics, employment, and the medical milieu dwindle their human capital. In line with the theory of discrimination by Gary Becker, employers incur financial losses when those minority

employees, who are inexpensive and at least as talented as the majority employees, are discriminated against during hiring (Gary Becker, 1971). If inequitable employers exist, minority workers will settle for less productive, under-qualified, and lower-paying jobs. Furthermore, employees facing prejudice at work may be thronged into insignificant positions or become jobless (Bergmann, 1971). Anyway, an economy is operating at its sub-optimal threshold with an inefficient use of the existing human capital.

CORRESPONDING STUDIES

A parallel frame of reference is derived through gender studies. Plenty of research affirms that gender disparity impedes economic growth (Berik et al., 2009). Several studies also reflect that disparity in female education attributes to subdued economic progress (Klasen, 2002; Klasen & Lamanna, 2009; Knowles et al., 2002). Extending this argument to the LGBT population, disbaring LGBT individuals in an academic milieu would cast a similar spell, in that subtle and overt ostracism of LGBT students would prompt school dropouts, leading to a rising number of unqualified and unemployed youth. Now, further broadening the argument, parents and a proper domestic structure play a significant role in shaping the children's personality. It augments their capabilities, contributing to a better socioeconomic status and good health (Cunha & Heckman, 2009).

Nevertheless, parents seldom contribute equally to each child. LGBT children may be subjected to persecution within the family structure, for instance, being deprived of proper food, housing, or schooling. A good amount of research reckons that men/boys have the privilege of healthier and more significant portions of meals than girls, thus restricting females' capabilities to undertake rewarding work that necessitates sound health (Pitt et al., 1990). Thus, the inequity toward LGBT within families and society casts its spell on the economy.

THE BUSINESS CASE

Inclusion and economic output are subtly intertwined through a compelling business case for LGBT diversity. The famous theory of discrimination by Harvard economist N. In his 'Principles of Microeconomics,' Gregory (Mankiw, 2013) states that discrimination is fundamentally unprofitable, as discriminating companies will be driven out of the market. This argument argues that fair treatment of LGBT people in organisations culminates in enhanced productivity and beneficial business outcomes. A multi-disciplinary research study reveals many positive results, notably improved physical and mental health and reduced employee turnover (Badgett et al., 2013; Li & Nagar, 2013). Button (2001) also emphasizes the ameliorated mental and job satisfaction for LGBT peers due to scaled-down workplace discrimination. Likewise, supportive workplaces also ease coming out and augmenting their psychological well (Rose Ragins et al., 2007). Moreover, a conducive environment translates into excellent workplace engagement and a more profound commitment from LGBT employees. In conjunction with the above argument, it can be corroborated that pro-LGBT policies, benefits, and practices effectuate enhanced work

associations between LGBT employees and their co-workers and supervisors (Brenner et al., 2010).

In line with many substantiating research works, which are closely connected but not LGBT-centric, the results of LGBT inclusion can be attributed to increased productivity and lesser labor costs, consequentially enhancing employer profits (Badgett et al., 2013). These increased monetary gains enkindle business expansion, thus boosting the economy. Furthermore, numerous studies have culminated in positive co-relation between pro-LGBT inclusive policies and financial metrics like stock prices (Jhonston & Malina, 2008; Li & Nagar, 2013; Shan et al., 2016; Wang & Schwarz, 2010), return on assets (Li & Nagar, 2013), output per worker (Shan et al., 2016) and employee innovation (Gao & Zhang, 2016). To sum up, collating these various substantiating research works can be corroborated in a unified postulation that embracing LGBT individuals and truly including them in the social structure stimulates the economy through reinforcing human capital and economic potentiality.

CONSULTING REPORTS

Renowned consultancies have also echoed the underlying principle that LGBT inclusion results in economic development through numerous comprehensive studies in this domain. Although little research has been done in India, research done in other countries reflects that productivity takes a hit substantially when LGBT employees remain closeted on their gender or sexual identities at work. This proliferates mistrust amongst colleagues, potentially undermining the organisation's effectiveness. (Banerji et al., 2012) It is essential to possess mental well-being and feel mentally and physically safe to be out at work for building reliable workplace relationships. According to Stonewall, an organisation working for equality and justice for lesbians, gay men, and bisexuals in the UK, 'concealing sexual orientation at work reduces productivity by up to 30 percent (Stonewall, 2010).

In 2018, 'LGBT Foundation' - a non-profit institute for LGBT, published a thought-provoking assessment that the LGBTQ community would have been the fourth largest economy per their GDP if their community existed as a country by themselves. Also, as per one of the leading advisory firms on corporate investments for LGBT consumers, 'LGBT capital,' the global spending power of LGBTQ consumers was estimated to be between the US \$3.6 trillion and US \$4.6 trillion per annum (LGBT Capital, 2018). In 2009, a renowned lesbian and gay marketing firm - Out Now Consulting, estimated the magnitude of the Indian LGBT+ economy to be the whopping US \$200 billion and its population to be 6 percent. These numbers indicate the US \$200 billion (6 percent of GDP) is the earned income from just 45 million gay and lesbian adults, a conservative figure for India's LGBT+ population, which would be higher now (Firstpost, 2013). In 2018, McKinsey produced a report, 'Delivering Through Diversity, based on a data set of over 1,000 companies in 12 countries, which looked at profitability measured as average EBIT margin. Companies in the top quartile for gender diversity on their executive teams were 21 percent more likely to have above-average profitability compared to companies in the fourth

quartile(Hunt et al., 2018). Also, Deloitte Australia produced a report in 2018, *The Diversity and Inclusion Revolution*, in which it cited one of its partners, Juliet Bourke's 2016 research which showed that organisations with inclusive cultures are: twice more likely to exceed financial targets, thrice more likely to be high performing, six times more likely to achieve better business outcomes (Bourke, 2016).

Now that we know that being inclusive is profitable for organisations, the reverse is also true. Discriminating against LGBTQ people also costs a lot of money(Shahani, 2020). Lee Badgett, an economist, and author of the landmark 2014 World Bank report on the economic cost of homophobia, estimated that homophobia could have cost India up to US \$30.8 billion, close to 1.7 percent of the country's potential GDP(Badgett et al., 2019). These numbers are conservative in that it has not included other subtle costs like that brain drain cost - people leaving because of the stigma of being an LGBT person. The Gallup World Poll 2012 surveyed 160 nations to determine whether a country, state or city - was a conducive place for lesbians and gays. The economists R. Florida and Mellander used a correlation between this data and GDP per capita and obtained a 0.72 score, which is significantly correlated(Miller & Parker, 2015). This implies that places that are friendlier to LGBT people have better economies. According to the 2014 Deloitte report on FDI and inclusive growth, growing foreign direct investment is a positive consequence of inclusive drives across companies.

CONCLUSION

LGBT people are subjected to unwarranted physical, psychological, and structural violence. They succumb to unreasonable discrimination in access to health, education, employment, and wages. This causes an indelible impression in the lives of LGBT people, affecting their physical and mental health. Besides the fact that these violations and means of ostracism have a detrimental effect on the individuals, they also engender a harmful impact on the economy as a whole. These fiscal costs comprise lost labor time, diminished productivity, lower investment in human capital, and insufficient allocation of human resources through unfair education and recruitment. The under-investment in human capital and suboptimal use of human resources can consequently damage the economy significantly. Hence, LGBT inclusion at work is imperative for a healthy economy and a holistic society. Business leaders must proactively devise policies and implement interventions to establish LGBT inclusion in the workplace. Essentially, the business and the moral cases for inclusion go hand in glove, fortifying each other's compelling argument in pursuit of an equalitarian society.

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DECLARATION OF CONFLICTING INTEREST

'The Author declares that there is no conflict of interest'.

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